

Characterization of Carbon Nanotube-Reinforced Polymer Composites

A. Haque^a, A. Ramasetty^a and S. Shamsuzzoha^b

^a*Department of Aerospace Engineering and Mechanics*

^b*Department of Metallurgical and Materials Engineering
The University of Alabama, Tuscaloosa*

ABSTRACT

In this work single walled carbon nanotube (SWNT) was used as reinforcing phase in epoxy matrix. The aim is to investigate the structures, analyze the load transfer efficiency at the interface regions and to determine the properties of carbon nanotube (CNT) based polymer composites (CNPC). The CNPC films have been manufactured by dispersing the SWNT in epoxy resin using an ultrasonic bath. SWNT used in this study was purified through acid solution process and dispersed in ethanol to minimize the agglomeration before mixing with the resin. The structures, dispersion characteristics, interphase of carbon nanotubes and matrix materials have been extensively studied by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) examinations. The results indicate that agglomeration of carbon nanotubes in epoxy is a major problem for processing CNPC. The tensile strength and modulus of both neat resin and the CNPC with 0.1% and 0.025% CNT by weight have been determined. The results show an increased strength (17%) and modulus (20%) for CNPC with 0.1% CNT in comparison to neat resin. It is to be noted that such enhancement in properties will possibly improve further if the problem of nanotube agglomeration is resolved. The load transfer efficiency at the interface along the length of the carbon nanotube has been studied using a modified shear lag model (MSLM) and finite element analysis (FEA). The stress distribution at the interface at various aspect ratios has been simulated. The results show significant differences between the shear lag model and finite element analysis (FEA) at lower aspect ratio (below 100) but at higher aspect ratios (above 1000) good agreement has been observed.

Keywords: carbon nanotube, composites, effective length, interfacial load transfer.

INTRODUCTION

The exceptional mechanical, thermal and electrical properties of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) show significant promises as a potential reinforcing phase in polymer matrix composites [1-3]. Typically, carbon nanotubes are long tiny cylinders of graphite structure with caps at each end. The length of these nanotubes ranges from few tens of nanometers to several micrometers, and the outer diameters usually extend from about 2.5 nm to 30 nm. These CNTs are mostly produced in the form of single-walled nanotubes (SWNTs) and multi-walled nanotubes (MWNTs). The most important features of carbon nanotubes are their extremely high stiffness combined with excellent resilience. For example, it has been reported that carbon nanotubes possess very high elastic modulus (higher than 1 TPa) and sustain large elastic strain up to 5% [4]. They are thermally stable up to 2800°C, and their thermal conductivity is about twice as high as diamond and electric current carrying capacity about 1000 times higher than copper wires. All these unique characteristics of CNTs show significant promises for developing nanotubes based composites to achieve improved structural, thermal, electrical and in some cases multifunctional properties. At

present very limited information is available in the literature about nanotubes based polymer composites [5-9]. Many critical issues related to processing, mechanics and properties of carbon nanotubes based polymer composites (CNPC) have been addressed in these references. The problems of agglomeration, uniform dispersion and adhesion of CNTs are major concerns in processing polymer nanocomposites [10]. The effective material properties of CNTs based composites has also been evaluated by some researchers through simulation using molecular dynamics and continuum mechanics approaches [11, 12]. These studies have shown that continuum approach has great potential for large scale analysis of nanocomposites. The interfacial bond characteristics and stress transfer between carbon nanotube and the matrix is of a great interest in the development of nanotube based composites. Qian reported the load transfer and deformation mechanisms in carbon-nanotube-polystyrene composites. Their experiments have shown that by addition of only 1% by weight of carbon nanotubes in polystyrene, the elastic stiffness increases by 36-42%, and the tensile strength increases by 25% [4]. TEM study also shows composite deformation mechanisms and interfacial bonding between multiwalled nanotube and polymer matrix. Lourie et-al [13], reported the buckling and collapse of carbon nanotubes/epoxy composite structure. They found that the shrinkage of an epoxy matrix after curing could generate a substantial high compressive stress to embedded nanotubes. The mechanics related to load transfer in conventional short fiber composites using shear lag model has been addressed by Cox [14]. In his work, Cox assumed that the rate of load transfer from matrix to fiber is proportional to the difference between axial displacement at a point in the fiber and the corresponding displacement at the same point in the matrix without the fiber present. Hsueh [15] extended this shear lag model proposed by Cox to platelets. Later Tsai [16] applied Hsueh's two-dimensional stress transfer model to nanoclay composites. He calculated the effective length, L_{eff} , axial stress, σ_f and shear stress, τ_i at the nanoclay/matrix interface.

In this paper, the model that Tsai applied to nanoclay platelet reinforced composite is extended to carbon nanotube reinforced polymer composite. All the parameters like the effective length, L_{eff} , the axial stress, σ_f and shear stress, τ_i of the SWNT/matrix interface are calculated. The results in analytical method are compared with finite element analysis. This paper also focused on the manufacturing and properties of CNPC. Thin films of CNPC were manufactured with varying percentages of SWNT. The dispersion of SWNT in the resin was studied by TEM and tensile properties of carbon nanotube based composites were also characterized.

EXPERIMENTAL, ANALYTICAL AND FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Materials and Manufacturing

Thin films of carbon nanotubes/epoxy were manufactured with various percentages of SWNT. The SWNTs used in processing composite films were produced by arc discharge method. In arc-discharge method the graphite anode is evaporated and the soot is deposited on the cathode. This cathodic soot is not amorphous, but contains long hollow fibers called nanotubes. The soot is not entirely nanotubes but it also contains impurities. Mainly there are two types of impurities contained in the cathodic soot, the metallic impurities and the amorphous graphite. Metallic impurities are due to the catalyst and can be removed by using acid solution of 3M HCl. Thermal oxidation is done using H_2S-O_2 gas mixture to remove the amorphous carbon particles preferentially [17]. The SWNT that was received from MER Corp., Tucson, AZ was 75-80 wt% pure which was further purified through acid solution process. In this process SWNT was suspended in 3 M HCl solution at room temperature for 24 hr. After 24 hr, the supernatant liquid (the liquid lying above a precipitate) was gradually poured off and the sediment was suspended in

deionized water. The procedure was repeated more than three times. Finally, the sample was dried at 150 °C for 24 hr. Fig. 1a-b shows TEM micrographs of tangled, spaghetti-like SWNT that are used in this study. These are basically the micrographs of as received SWNT. The diameters of SWNT were observed in the range of 0.9-1.2 nm. The dispersion of CNTs in the resin is a major concern in manufacturing CNPC. A schematic of various forms of dispersion of carbon nanotubes in composites is shown in Fig. 2.

To achieve good dispersion initially the SWNTs were dispersed in ethanol in an ultrasonic bath at room temperature for 1hr. After 1 hr. of dispersion with ethanol, the SC-15 epoxy resin was

Fig1. TEM micrographs of SWNT (a) High magnification (b) Low magnification

added and the dispersion in the ultrasonic bath was continued for another 1 hr. Then the mixture was kept in an oven at 80°C until the ethanol evaporates. When ethanol was completely evaporated, the hardener was added (the resin to hardener ratio was 10: 3). Finally, the mixture was stirred for another 15 mins. Thin films were made by pouring the nanotube-resin mixture on a glass plate. The mixture was vitrified for 2 hr. at 60°C. The post curing of the CNPC was done at 100°C for 5hr. Two types of CNPC thin films with 0.025% and 1.0 % by weight of SWNT were manufactured by using the above mentioned technique.

Microscopic Examinations

In manufacturing nanocomposites with carbon nanotubes and the nanoparticles, dispersion is one of the major problems. The dispersion of CNT in the matrix and the interface characteristics between CNT and resin were investigated using both optical and transmission electron microscopic (TEM) examinations. In TEM analysis specially prepared specimens in form of tiny circular discs of diameter 3mm and thickness of 150 nm were used. The specimens were thinned at the center of the circular disc using both dimpling and ion milling process. Special care was taken, so that excess ion milling was not done which would cause a hole in the middle of the specimen.

Fig. 2 Dispersion of nanotubes in composite [10]

Mechanical Testing

Tensile tests were performed on dog bone shaped specimens of CNPC to determine the mechanical properties of nanocomposites. Figure 3a shows the specimen design of the CNPC used in this study. Figs. 3b and c show the actual specimens made from the neat resin and CNPC.

Fig. 3 (a) Tensile specimen geometry (all dimensions in mm) (b) Neat resin specimen (c) CNPC specimen

Load Transfer Efficiency in CNPC

Analytical Method

Carbon nanotube reinforced polymer composite (CNPC) with uniformly distributed SWNTs is shown in Fig. 4(a). Fig. 4(b) shows representative volume element (RVE) used in the load transfer analysis. The uniform traction boundary condition was used on the RVE and the stress field was calculated using the shear lag model proposed by Cox [14]. This condition was different from the generally used uniform displacement condition which was used in the finite element analysis. While using the shear lag model the effect of the end gap was neglected. Fig. 5 shows the 2D unit cell model of carbon nanotube reinforced composites used in this study.

Fig. 4 Carbon Nanotube composite: (a) Uniformly distributed SWNT (b) RVE

Fig. 5 2D unit cell model

In the case of long SWNT in the matrix, the axial stress in the fiber increases from both ends under uniaxial loading and reaches to a saturated point at some fiber length. To achieve most of the saturation stress along the length of the nanotube the load transfer should be maximized. The effective length, L_{eff} is defined to determine the efficiency of the load transfer from the matrix to the carbon nanotube. The effective length, L_{eff} of the SWNT is the length in which the equivalent amount of the saturated load is carried and mathematically defined as follows:

$$\sigma_f^s L_{\text{eff}} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-L}^L \sigma_f dy \quad (1)$$

where σ_f is axial stress and σ_f^s is saturated stress in the SWNT.

Following the derivation by Hsueh [15] using modified shear-lag model and the expression by Tsai and Sun [16] for platelet reinforcement, the axial stress σ_f in the carbon nanotube and the shear stress τ_i at the nanotube/matrix interface are defined as follows:

$$\sigma_f = \frac{(R_o - R_i + b)E_f \sigma_o}{(R_o - R_i)E_f + bE_m} + Ae^{\alpha y} + Be^{-\alpha y} \quad (2)$$

$$\tau_i = -(R_o - R_i) [A\alpha e^{\alpha y} - B\alpha e^{-\alpha y}] \quad (3)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{b} \left\{ \frac{3[(R_o - R_i)E_f + bE_m]G_m}{(R_o - R_i)E_f \cdot E_m} \right\}^{1/2},$$

E_f and E_m are the moduli of elasticity of the SWNT and matrix. Coefficients A and B can be determined using the two boundary conditions, $\sigma_t = \sigma_o$ at $y = L$ and $\tau_i = 0$ at $y = 0$.

Substituting coefficients A and B in (2), σ_f becomes

$$\sigma_f = \frac{(R_o - R_i + b) E_f \sigma_o}{(R_o - R_i) E_f + bE_m} + \frac{e^{\alpha y} + e^{-\alpha y}}{e^{\alpha L} + e^{-\alpha L}} \left[1 - \frac{(R_o - R_i + b) E_f}{(R_o - R_i) E_f + bE_m} \right] \sigma_o \quad (4)$$

Now, saturated stress, σ_f^s can be determined by letting L to infinity in equation 1

$$\sigma_f^s = \frac{(R_o - R_i + b) E_f \sigma_o}{(R_o - R_i) E_f + bE_m} \quad (5)$$

Substituting σ_f & σ_f^s into equation (1), we finally get the expression of effective length, L_{eff} for SWNT as follows:

$$L_{\text{eff}} = L + \tanh(\alpha L) \frac{\left[1 - \frac{(R_o - R_i + b) E_f \sigma_o}{(R_o - R_i) E_f + bE_m} \right]}{\alpha \left[\frac{(R_o - R_i + b) E_f \sigma_o}{(R_o - R_i) E_f + bE_m} \right]} \quad (6)$$

The effective length is independent of the magnitude of the applied load. L_{eff} is calculated for various aspect ratios and the specifications of the SWNT.

Finite element analysis

The finite element analysis of the CNPC was done using a quarter symmetric model. Eight noded hybrid solid element (C3D8I) was used in the analysis [18]. This solid element has extra incompatible deformation modes in addition to the displacement degrees of freedom. These degrees of freedom eliminate the parasitic shear stresses that are observed in regular displacement elements if there are loaded in bending. Table 1 shows the properties of the SWNT and the matrix that were used in the analysis. The quarter symmetric geometric model of the CNPC is shown in Fig. 6. Finite element analysis was carried out at various aspect ratios of SWNT. Loading conditions applied in the model was similar to that considered in the analytical study. In this study, one end of the CNPC was fixed and a pressure load was applied at the other end. The stress distribution at the interface of the matrix and the SWNT was investigated. The results obtained in FEA study were compared with the analytical results.

Property	SWNT	Matrix
Modulus of elasticity, E (Pa)	1×10^{12}	1×10^9
Poisson's ratio, ν	0.35	0.27
Type of element	Solid	Solid

Table 1 Properties of SWNT and matrix used in finite element analysis

Fig. 6 Quarter symmetric FEA model of CNPC

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

CNPCs were manufactured through dispersion of SWNT in epoxy resin using ultrasonic bath. The dispersion of SWNTs in the resin has been studied carefully through optical and transmission electron microscopy. The optical micrographs are shown in Figs. 7a & 8a. It is observed that the SWNTs are dispersed evenly in agglomerated form. TEM micrograph in Fig. 7b also shows bundle of carbon nanotubes in nanoscale. The maximum length of these CNTs can be approximately 400 nm. Since the diameter of SWNT is approximately in the range of 1 nm, this bundle may consist of approximately 250 SWNTs. The problems of agglomeration of CNTs in epoxy resin are clearly visible from all these micrographs. In Fig. 8b, the diffraction pattern of CNT shows that it is in the crystalline form.

Fig. 7 (a) Optical Micrograph (b) TEM of 0.1% SWNT CNPC

Fig. 8 (a) Optical Micrograph (b) Diffraction pattern 0.025% SWNT CNPC

Fig. 9 shows the stress-strain plots of both neat resin and carbon nanotube/epoxy polymer nanocomposites. The stress-strain plots appear to be linear up to approximately 2% strain and then eventually become nonlinear until final failure. The enhanced strength and modulus of nanotube reinforced composites with 0.1% by wt SWNT are clearly observed from the plots in Fig. 9. The strength and modulus data for all the cases are provided in Table 2. The results show almost 20% increase in modulus and 17% increase in yield strength for CNPC with 0.1% SWNT. But the CNPC with 0.025% CNTs rather show almost same modulus and little reduced strength as compared to neat resin. It is to be noted that these modulus and strength increment are mostly due to bundle of nanotubes rather than well dispersed single-walled carbon nanotubes.

Further studies are required to resolve the agglomeration problem of these CNPCs and the results will be presented in the technical presentation.

Fig. 9 Stress vs strain plot for neat epoxy resin and CNPC

Specimen	Modulus (MPa)	% change in modulus	Yield Strength (MPa)	% change in yield strength	Ultimate Strength (MPa)	% change in ultimate strength
Neat	14.17	-	34.3	-	45.65	-
0.025 % SWNT	15.5	9.39	34.21	-0.26	42.4	-7.12
0.1% SWNT	17.1	20.68	40.16	17.08	52.3	14.57

Table 2 Tensile test data

The stress distribution at the interface of CNT and matrix along the length of nanotube is shown in Fig. 10. The analysis was done by finite element method at various aspect ratios (length/diameter) of the nanotube and the axial stress distribution is shown only for half of the tube length. The results show zero stress at the end of the tube indicating no stress transfer. The stress level increases gradually with increased tube length and reaches to a saturation point with a plateau at 32 nm tube length. Such saturation point was not attained with lower aspect ratios (less than 25).

Fig. 11 shows a comparison of L_{eff}/L at various aspect ratios determined by finite element analysis and shear lag model. In both the cases L_{eff}/L increases with increased aspect ratios. But such increases are significantly higher at lower aspect ratios. At very low aspect ratio (100), the differences in magnitude of L_{eff}/L between FEA and shear lag model was approximately 80%. These differences are observed to be significantly reduced at higher aspect ratios (1000-5000).

Moreover, in all the cases the magnitude of L_{eff}/L determined by the shear lag model was comparatively higher than the result obtained from FEA study. Both the FEA and shear lag model almost converges at $l/d = 5000$.

Fig. 10 Axial stress along the fiber length from finite element analysis

Fig. 11 Load transfer efficiency (L_{eff}/L) as a function of aspect ratio (L/D)

CONCLUSIONS

The carbon nanotube based epoxy films have been processed and the TEM results show bundle of nanotubes rather than well dispersed single walled carbon nanotubes in epoxy resin. This agglomeration problem needs to be resolved in future study. Both tensile modulus and yield

strength are approximately 20% and 17% higher for 0.1 % CNTs based composites in comparison to neat resin. Such enhancement in strength and modulus are attributed mostly due to the effects of nanotube bundles rather than SWNTs. The issues of load transfer efficiency at the interface have been investigated by both finite element and shear lag model. At higher aspect ratios the L_{eff}/L ratios show reasonable agreements between FEA and shear lag model.

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